

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D3.5 ANALYTICS ON THE SUBMITTED PROPOSALS OPEN CALL 1

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this Public report is to provide a summary of relevant statistics and findings from STADIEM Open Call #1. The information will be published on the website of the project.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The STADIEM Open Call #1 was launched on 1st February 2021 (12:00 PM CET) and closed on 31st March 2021 (17:00 CET). This open call aimed to attract and engage 40 promising tech start-ups, scale-ups and SMEs to join the STADIEM 4-stage pilot programme, with a duration of 14 months and a budget of 1,93M€.

The target was start-ups, scale-ups and SMEs with innovative products and highscaling and piloting potential whose solutions can be integrated/ incorporated in the European corporate / media sector and beyond, thus developing new products and services which address current media challenges as identified in the STADIEM Open Call #1 Guide for Applicants.

This document provides a summary of the achieved results including relevant statistics and findings from open call # 1, and will be published on STADIEM website.

2 OPEN CALL 1 STATISTICS

The first STADIEM Open Call was automatically closed on 31st March, 17:00 CET (Brussels time). In total 418 applications were started on the F6S platform and 209 proposals have been finally submitted as presented in the chart below.

FIGURE 1 OPEN CALL RESULTS: FINALIZED OR IN PROGRES

2.1 PROFILE OF APPLICANTS

2.1.1 Countries

The first open call received proposals from 37 countries. It is possible to see a predominance of applications from the UK (37), Germany (24), Spain (13) and Estonia (13), followed by applications from France, Italy, Belgium and The Netherlands among others. A large number of countries were covered thanks to the communication and dissemination efforts in getting participants from all the eligible countries.

The geographical distribution of the submitted application is shown in the chart below.

FIGURE 2 NUMBER OF APPLICATIONS PER COUNTRY

2.1.2 STADIEM Selected Focus Areas

In this first open call, STADIEM allowed for applications within 7 established focus areas. Applicants were able to select between Archiving, Content Creation & Distribution, Content verification and Fight Against Disinformation, Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media, Journalism 4.0, Monetization and Moonshots (any new existing and interesting solutions related to media).

The distribution of applications received among the different focus areas can be seen in the figure below, which shows Content Creation and Distribution as the challenge chosen by the majority of applicants (41%), followed by Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media (30%), Moonshots (12%), Monetization (8%), Content verification and against disinformation (5%) and Archiving (4%).

FIGURE 3 DISTRIBUTION OF APPLICATIONS PER FOCUS AREA

2.1.3 Maturity Level

In first open call, applicants had to provide information about their current product status and maturity level. As shown in the figure below, the majority of applications have a fully functional product with paying customers (27%), recurring MRR (20%) and private beta MVP (20%).

FIGURE 4 TECHNOLOGICAL LEVEL: CURRENT PRODUCT STATUS

2.1.4 Business Type

STADIEM's first open call requested for applicants whose business model is mainly B2B or in case of B2C, they have B2B partnerships.

As indicated in the figure below, almost all applicants managed to fulfill the requirement.

FIGURE 5 APPLICANTS PER TYPE OF BUSINESS

2.2 SELECTED PROPOSALS

A filtering procedure was applied to remove non-eligible proposals. Eligibility checking has verified that:

- the proposing entity is a legal entity eligible for EC funding under the rules of H2020
- the proposing entity is a SME
- additional eligibility rules as expressed in the Guide for Applicants are followed (e.g. checking that a legal entity has not submitted more than one proposal, the legal entity has a business model which is B2B 80% (if B2C, then needs to provide examples of B2B Partnerships).
- the requested application documents (company financials) are uploaded in the requested STADIEM template
- the applications is submitted in the English Language
- have accepted the terms under the Declaration of Honour

Out of the 209 submitted proposals in the STADIEM Open Call #1, 16 have been considered not eligible

After the evaluation process, 40 proposals have been selected from the 209 submitted (19,1%).

2.2.1 Summary of selected proposals

The 40 selected proposals were among 18 eligible countries, established mainly in the EU.

FIGURE 6 AWARDEE PER COUNTRY

The focus areas addressed by the awardees reflect the overall distribution of the different focus areas, with the majority covering Content Creation & Distribution (32%) and Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media (32%).

FIGURE 7 DISTRIBUTION OF AWARDEES PER FOCUS AREA

The majority of the awardees in the first open call already have a fully functional product, several with paying customers (37%) and recurring MRR (28%).

FIGURE 8 AWARDEE TECHNOLOGICAL LEVEL

All the selected companies are B2B operational, with a few that also provide a B2C solution.

FIGURE 9 AWARDEE BUISNESS MODEL

Most of the selected companies are relatively young – being operational for 2-4 years. Only 3 of the selected companies have been operational for more than 8 years. An overview is provided in the figure below.

FIGURE 10 AWARDEE: SME AGE

